

10th International Symposium on Syrphidae
Lesvos Greece
8th - 12th September 2019

PROGRAMME
&
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

MYTILENE 2019

Organizing Committee

Theodora Petanidou, University of the Aegean, Mytilene, Greece
Thomas Tscheulin, University of the Aegean, Mytilene, Greece
Ante Vujić, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia
Jelena Ačanski, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia
Marija Miličić, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia
Marina Janković, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia
Dubravka Milić, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia
Ana Grković, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia
Laura Likov, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

International Scientific Committee

Francis Gilbert, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, United Kingdom
Gunilla Ståhls, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland
Santos Rojo, University of Alicante, Alicante, Spain
Mirian N. Morales, Universidade Federal de Lavras, Lavras, Brazil
John T. Smit, European Invertebrate Survey – Netherlands, Leiden, the Netherlands
Ximo Mengual, Zoological Research Museum Alexander Koenig, Bonn, Germany
Snežana Radenković, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia
Mihajla Đan, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

Congress Venue

Department of Geography, University of the Aegean, University Hill, 81100, Mytilene, Greece

Sponsored by

University of the Aegean

Department of Geography, University of the Aegean

Supported by

University of the Aegean

Symposium logo: Jelena Ačanski

Identifying hoverfly functional groups in Southeast Europe in response to different land-cover types

Marija Miličić^{*1,2}, Tamara Jurca³, Snežana Popov³, Marina Janković³, Pedro Cardoso², Jelena Ačanski¹ & Ante Vujčić³

¹BioSense Institute – Research Institute for Information Technologies in Biosystems, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia; e-mail: marija.milicic@biosense.rs, acanskijelena@gmail.com

²LIBRe – Laboratory for Integrative Biodiversity Research, Finnish Museum of Natural History, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland; e-mail: pedro.cardoso@helsinki.fi

³Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia; e-mail: tamara.jurca@dbe.uns.ac.rs, snezana.jovicic@dbe.uns.ac.rs, marinaj@dbe.uns.ac.rs, ante.vujic@dbe.uns.ac.rs

Keywords: conservation; clustering; functional traits; perturbations; Syrphidae

The functional group is defined as a set of species that show a similar response to the environment or similar effects on ecosystem processes. Functional classification often has two different objectives: one is to investigate the effects of species on characteristics of ecosystem (functional groups effect), and the second is to explore the type of the response to changes in the environment, such as destruction of the environment, availability of resources and climate change (functional response groups). Identification of functional response groups may help to understand and predict how certain aspects of the community and the ecosystem can be affected by environmental changes.

In this study, our aim was to divide the 564 hoverfly species recorded in Southeast Europe based on their functional traits into functional groups using cluster analysis, and to use these groups to assess how functional biodiversity of hoverflies is related to different land-cover types.

The combination of information on functional groups and land-cover stratification enables a concise, comprehensive, direct assessment of hoverfly biodiversity in relation to land cover. These types of analyses provide a better base for the formulation of conservation and biodiversity policy.

Acknowledgements: This work was funded by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia, grant nos OI173002 and III43002, the Provincial Secretariat for Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia, grant no. 0601-504/3, and the H2020 Project ANTARES, grant no. 664387.